

FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION USING CREDIT CARDS: THE CASE OF JOINT STOCK COMMERCIAL BANK FOR FOREIGN TRADE OF VIET NAM

HA HONG NGUYEN

Associate Professor, School Economics and Law, Tra Vinh University, Vietnam. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7404-0599. Corresponding Author Email: travinh@tvu.edu.vn CP: honghaicbtv@yahoo.com.vn

Abstract

The objective of this study is to discover the factors affecting customer satisfaction in the process of using credit cards issued by Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade of Vietnam in the Mekong Delta provinces, Viet Nam, including: branch of Tra Vinh province, branch of Vinh Long province, branch of Ben Tre province, branch of Soc Trang province and branch of An Giang province; From there, helping the Bank develop appropriate customer care policies. The study was conducted by collecting primary data from 260 customers who have been using Vietcombank's credit cards. Using multivariate regression analysis method by, the research has found 5 factors affecting customer satisfaction: Tangible means, Reliability, Assurance, response ability and Empathy. In which, Reliability has the strongest impact. On the basis of the analysis results, the author proposes policy implications to improve the quality of credit card services of Vietcombank and thereby help the bank to improve satisfaction when using Vietcombank's credit card service in the future.

Keywords: Factors, satisfaction, credit card, Vietcombank, solution

JEL Classification Code: D23, G41, G21, J28, R23...

1. INTRODUCTION

In the trend of shopping and consumption at home and abroad of people is increasing. Competition among banks in attracting customers to use credit cards is fierce. Card customers are also becoming more aware of the alternatives offered and the rising standards of service in a competitive trend that has resulted in raising their expectations (Valarie A. Zeithaml, Mary Jo Bitner & Dwayne Gremler (2000)), as a result, customers are becoming more and more concerned about the quality of service they experience (Charles Mwatsika, 2014). The service that banks provide from the customer's evaluation side as a basis to improve service quality (Benjamin Schneider & Susan S. White (2004) and Parasuraman A, Zeithaml VA, Berry LL (1988), many previous studies have shown hypothesized and researched the relationship of the positive influence of the quality of banking and satisfaction services of customers, such as the research of Nguyen Thanh Vu & Ha Thi Thanh Thuy (2021), Nguyen Viet Hung (2019) and of Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019), Charles Mwatsika (2014), Gaura Nautiyal (2014), Rubogora Felix (2017). The authors assert that the higher the quality of banking service is appreciated by customers, the higher their satisfactions will be. Increased (Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019), Charles Mwatsika (2014)) and Sasser, W.E., Olsen, R.P. and Wyckoff, D.D. (1978).

Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade of Vietnam (Vietcombank) s one of the largest joint stock commercial banks in Vietnam. Vietcombank deployed many typical credit card

products such as: Amex, Visa, Master and JCB as well as coordinated with many partners in the area to increase the number of card acceptors. Over the years, in the period 2017-2021, the number of credit cards registered at Vietcombank increased by an average of 20% per year, accounting for over 15% of the number of credit cards issued in Vietnam (Vietcombank, 2022). Although the number of customers registering to use credit cards has increased over the years, credit card revenue has increased slowly. This poses the need to study the customer's satisfactions with the quality of Vietcombank's credit card service, and the factors affecting the customer's satisfaction as a basis for Vietcombank to improve the quality of card service. Their credit to maintain existing customers who always use credit card services and contribute to attracting new customers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Fauz Khamis, and Rosemaliza AbRashid (2018). Findings indicate that customers are satisfied with the Islamic banking services provided by Tanzania banks. However, it has been found that customers are attracted by compliance, tangibility and reliability of the banks. The findings further indicate a significant relationship between service quality and customers' satisfaction. Indeed, empathy, compliance and reliability were found to be the only significant predictors of customers' satisfaction. The study suggest that there is large number of Muslim and non-Muslims communities who are interested in Islamic modes of finance and banking. Banks have potential to increase customers' base by improving the quality of their services. Essentially, banks must focus on complying with Islamic principles, improving reliability and empathy, as they statistically influence customers' satisfaction. Besides, Charles Mwatsika (2014) studied customer satisfaction with ATM card service quality in Malawi Branch. Survey with data analysis of 353 ATM card users with factors in service quality model including: Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibles. The results found that the service quality aspects are significantly correlated with customer Satisfaction with ATM services. Reliability is the most important aspect.

Gaura Nautiyal (2014) measures the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction in India. The survey of 225 customers was conducted across Delhi through a survey of 22 observed variables based on the SERVQUAL model: Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, and Tangible Means. The results show that there are exists a linear relationship between Customer Satisfaction and the factors of service quality. Chew Wen Jing et al (2018) surveyed 200 credit card customers in the respective states: Sabah, Selangor and Johor to evaluate the relationship between customers satisfaction with credit card service quality in Malaysia. The result proved that 05 factors: tangible means, Reliability, Assurance, Empathy, and Responsiveness. Rubogora Felix (2017) determined the level of customer satisfaction with banking services related to the quality of different services provided by the bank at Banque Populaire du Rwanda, Kigali branch. Service quality is studied based on the SERVQUAL model, including: tangible means, Reliability, Assurance, Empathy, and Responsiveness. The author collected primary data from 498 customers using convenient sampling technique, this result is similar to the study of Khan & Fasih (2014) and Raja (2014) studied the factors affecting satisfaction in banking sector of Pakistan. Data were collected through a structured

questionnaire survey from 72 respondents. The results of this study show that there is a significant relationship between service quality attributes and customer satisfaction. Tran Thi Kim Chi (2019) based on SERVPERF include Reliability, Responsiveness, Service Capability, Empathy, and Tangible Means. The sample was selected by convenient sampling method with 392 questionnaires included in the analysis. Besides, Le Ngoc Diep et al (2017) proved that the factors including: Reliability, Service Efficiency, Service Capacity, Empathy, Tangible Means, Credibility affecting the satisfaction of individual customers with the quality of domestic debit card services at Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade - Dong Nai Branch.

Le Thi Thu Hong et al (2014) considered 190 customers using payment card services at agencies, units, businesses and customers coming to the branch to make transactions. The result of including: Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangible Means. Moreover, Nguyen Viet Hung (2019) studies the factors affecting customer satisfaction with card services at Agribank, Kien Giang province. There are 7 independent factors affecting: Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibles, Network, and Price.

Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019) examined 779 Individual customers using ATM card service of Vietcombank Vinh Long. The research on calibration of SERVQUAL scale and use of SERVPERF model to study the relationship between quality of ATM card service and customer satisfaction. There are 7 independent factors affecting: Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibles, Network, and Price. Nguyen Thi Thu (2016) studies the factors affecting customer satisfaction using ATM card services of banks in Hanoi. The factors include: Reliability, Responsiveness, Tangibility, Assurance, Empathy, Convenience, Service Price by 375 survey questionnaires were included in the analysis and distributed to research customers using ATM card services in Hanoi.

Nguyen Thanh Vu & Ha Thi Thanh Thuy (2021) surveyed 304 customers who are using credit cards of Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Investment and Development of Vietnam, Phu My Hung branch. The study demonstrated 5 factors affecting customer satisfaction using credit cards: Reliability, Responsiveness, Tangible Means, Empathy, Assurance and an additional factor is Service Cost. Studies domestically and internationally have focused on assessing customer satisfaction about banking products and services, specifically ATM cards, in many different banks around the world. However, there has not been any research to evaluate the satisfaction of customers using credit cards in Vietnam specifically at a bank like Vietcombank. The authors inherit the comparative studies and research models on satisfaction to conduct research at Vietcombank.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Based on SERVQUAL and SERVPERF models (Cronin JJ, Taylor SA (1992) and Oliver, R.L. (1980) are often used mainly in the research on the quality of service to SHL of customers (Gronroos C (1984) and Oliver, R.L. (1980)). Some studies add a few factors to better understand the customers' satisfaction using credit cards of Vietcombank.

$$Y_i = B_0 + B_1 X_{1i} + B_2 X_{2i} + B_3 X_{3i} + \dots + e_i$$

In which:

Y_i : dependent variable (is the satisfaction of customers using credit card services)

X_i : independent variable, credit card service quality factors.

Figure 1: Summary of variables in the research model

(Source: proposed research model)

Table 1: Summary of variables in the model

Ordinal number	Symbols	Explanation	Sources	Expected signs
		Dependent variable		
	Y	Satisfaction	Synthesis of domestic and international studies.	+/-
	X	Independent variables		
1	X_1	Tangible Means	Cronin & Taylor (1992); Nguyen Thanh Vu & Ha Thi Thanh Thuy (2021), Nguyen Viet Hung (2019), Le Ngoc Diep & et al (2017), Le Thi Thu Hong et al (2014), Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019), Charles Mwatsika (2014).	+

2	X ₂	Reliability	Fauz Khamis, and Rosemaliza AbRashid (2018), Gaura Nautiyal (2014), Chew Wen Jing (2018), Nguyen Viet Hung (2019), Le Ngoc Diep et al (2017), Le Thi Thu Hong et al (2014), Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019)	+
3	X ₃	Assurance	Chew Wen Jing (2018), Aaroni Ulaya (2017), Charles Mwatsika (2014), Rubogora Felix (2017), Rubogora Felix (2017), Lê Thị Thu Hồng & ctg (2014).	+
4	X ₄	Response ability	Raja (2014), Rubogora Felix (2017), Cronin and Taylor (1992), Nguyen Thanh Vu & Ha Thi Thanh Le Ngoc Diep et al (2017), Le Thi Thu Hong et al (2014), Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019)), Charles Mwatsika (2014)	+
5	X ₅	Empathy	Fauz Khamis, and Rosemaliza AbRashid (2018), Gaura Nautiyal (2014), Chew Wen Jing et al (2018), Charles Mwatsika (2014), Cronin and Taylor (1992), Nguyen Thanh Vu & Ha Thi Thanh Thuy (2021), Nguyen Viet Hung (2019), Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019)	+

(Source: compiled from review studies).

Survey sample collecting data according to the formula $N \geq 5k$, where: N is the survey sample, k is the number of observed variables (Hoang Trong and Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc, 2008). The study is expected to have 28 observed variables (including 25 observed variables of independent factors and 3 observed variables of the dependent variable Satisfactions). The fit sample size is 140. In multivariable regression, the minimum sample is $N=50 + 8k$ where k is the number of independent variables. The study has 6 independent variables. The required sample is 98. The author plans to distribute 300 questionnaires. The subject of the survey is the customer who is using the credit card service of Vietcombank.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phenomenon of autocorrelation: Durbin-Watson coefficient has the value $d = 1.831$. Durbin-Watson results table with sample size $n = 260$, degrees of freedom $k' = k - 1 = 5$, significance level 5%, $dL = 1.76558$, $dU = 1.82803$. We have $dU = 1.82803 < d = 1.831 < 4 - dL = 2.23442$. Thereby, it shows that there is no autocorrelation phenomenon.

Table 2. Multivariate regression results

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		standardized coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Standard errors (Std. Error)	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	0,078	0,155		0,502	0,616		
	X1	0.146	0,052	0.160	4,424	0,001	0,414	1.137
	X2	0.246	0,039	0.280	7,138	0,000	0,519	1.191
	X3	0.187	0,052	0.219	3,476	0,000	0,421	1.300
	X4	0.159	0,061	0.170	2,119	0,000	0,280	1.144
	X5	0.221	0,040	0.273	4,498	0,000	0,496	1.284

a. Dependent Variable: SATISFACTION (Y).

Table 3: Table of significant variables

Variable codes	Coefficient β	Sig.	VIF
Constant (C)		0,616	0,000
X1 (Tangible Means)	0.160	0.001***	1.137
X2 (Reliability)	0.280	0.000***	1.191
X3 (Assurance)	0.219	0.000***	1.300
X4 (Response ability)	0.170	0.000***	1.144
X5 (Empathy)	0.273	0.000***	1.284

Notes: ***, alternative reliability 99%,

Looking at Table 2, the model analysis results show that the adjusted R2 coefficient of the model is 0.716, which proves that the ability to reflect the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The Sig. F coefficients of the model are all much smaller than the significance level $\alpha = 5\%$, so the regression model is significant.

From the results of primary data analysis summarized in Table 3, it can be shown that there is a Sig value. < 0.05 in all variables in which, the variable “Tangible Means” has the value Sig. = 0.001; variable “Reliability” has value Sig. 0.000; the remaining variables have Sig values. = 0.000. Thus, the regression coefficients of these variables are significant and well used in the model.

From the regression coefficients synthesized from the results of data analysis, the regression equation is obtained:

$$\text{Satisfaction} = 0 + 0.160 \times \text{Tangible Means} + 0.280 \times \text{Reliability} + 0.219 \times \text{Assurance} + 0.170 \times \text{Response ability} + 0.273 \times \text{Empathy}$$

The regression coefficients are all positive, showing the relationship between the independent

factors: Tangibles, Reliability, Assurance, Responsiveness and Empathy to Customer's satisfactions with credit card service of Vietcombank is the same direction. This is consistent with the original hypothesis of the author. So all hypotheses are accepted. The results of the study all factors have an influence on customer satisfaction.

This once again affirms that the theoretical basis of inheritance and the results of the study do not contradict previous studies related to the topic of domestic authors Tran Thi Kim Chi (2019), Le Ngoc Diep. & ctg (2017) , Le Thi Thu Hong et al (2014), Nguyen Viet Hung (2019), Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019), Nguyen Thi Thu (2016), Nguyen Thanh Vu & Ha Thi Thanh Thuy (2021); foreign authors Aaroni Ulaya (2017), Charles Mwatsika (2014), Gaura Nautiyal (2014), Chew Wen Jing (2018), Rubogora Felix (2017), Khan & Fasih (2014), Raja (2014). However, the degree of influence of service quality factors on satisfaction is different in each topic.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Reliability

The process of providing services, modern IT infrastructure, using advanced security methods, related to the provision of credit card services of Vietcombank performed as committed, on time, delivered The translation is done at the first time and reduces the error in the transaction. Therefore, Vietcombank needs to have a plan to periodically review and evaluate the process of providing services, systems and electronic payment technology to make timely adjustments when problems arise. In addition, focus on investing in upgrading the system, updating modern technology, deploying new technology solutions that integrate many versatile utilities of credit card services and improve security. New technologies for credit cards such as touchless payment, chip security technology, strong authentication technology and digital signatures... ensure maximum transaction safety and confidentiality. This shows the reliability of service quality and creates peace of mind for customers.

Reasonable process, modern technology and security make credit card transactions smooth, fast and accurate, ensuring safety, without errors and risks. When customers trust and have confidence when performing credit card transactions, bringing work efficiency to customers, customers will be satisfied and continue to use credit card services of Vietcombank.

Empathy

Be serious and maintain the professional cultural environment of Vietcombank in accordance with the rules, manners and punctuality of work. At the same time, Vietcombank needs to have its own hotline that operates smoothly 24/7 via phone and chat channel to promptly receive problems and arising problems of customers. On the one hand, the situation can be quickly handled, on the other hand, reduce the overload with Vietcombank's general hotline. Expanding the network of locations accepting Vietcombank's credit cards in combination with payment cooperation to a variety of services in the province with attractive incentive programs to increase card usage. Credit with customers as well as credit card acceptance points as a connection channel of the bank with customers using credit cards.

Vietcombank needs to have a plan to add more personnel, combine training and in-depth training, to ensure that all employees of Vietcombank understand the products and services, especially specialized staff. Empathy for credit card services, firmly grasp the characteristics of each card in terms of features, uses, costs, and interest calculation. From there, giving appropriate advice to each customer, and corresponding spending solutions and suitable to the individual financial situation of each customer. This shows empathy in the quality of credit card services, understanding customer needs, meeting each need will make them more satisfied.

Assurance

Vietcombank needs to invest in IT to ensure that customer's account information is always confidential, not to reveal data to the public to take advantage of stealing important information, causing financial risks to customers. At the same time, in customer activities, customer data is important. Therefore, it is necessary to have solutions for backing up customer data safely, proactively in situations when cybercriminals are increasingly sophisticated with many tricks.

Raise awareness of customers when making transactions through credit cards. Banks need to ensure the provision of necessary knowledge and skills for customers to remember to be safe in their credit card transactions and handle them proactively and quickly when there is a problem. Specifically, (1) Know how to block the online payment feature and lock the credit card right through the bank's application when in doubt; (2) When detecting suspicious signs or revealing confidential information, customers must know the hotline number and contact Vietcombank's 24/7 hotline in a timely manner. Improve the "level of assurance", always improve service quality based on feedback from customers. This helps Vietcombank have an objective view of its operations. On that basis, Vietcombank resolved quickly and responsibly, maintaining a better image of Vietcombank with customers.

Bank employees have a great role in helping the bank grow. They directly work with customers, find out and give the most suitable advice, answer questions about credit card services and help customers understand the credit card services they use. If they feel suitable, understand the advice, customers will use the service. At the same time, not only focusing on the features and benefits of credit cards with customers, Vietcombank staff need to advise customers to control their spending well, in accordance with the payment time, to avoid overdue interest penalties. From there, create trust for customers. Vietcombank's teller at the counter needs (1) to actively advise, explain in detail and recommend spending to customers in cases that may be taken advantage of; (2) Instructing customers how to recognize Vietcombank's official website when it is encrypted and has absolute security at the link; (3) How to make transactions securely, what information is provided, what information needs to be kept confidential. Thereby, helping customers limit financial risks.

Responsibility

In order for customers' transactions to be always satisfied, Vietcombank's facilities and payment infrastructure should always be periodically reviewed and upgraded to meet technical standards, and at the same time ensure secure new and modern technology and solutions to

secure customers' data. Since then, the processing of credit card transactions is done quickly and accurately. Modern infrastructure and systems are important along with the technical team of Vietcombank. Vietcombank's specialized technical team needs to monitor the system 24/7, ensuring the system's readiness and processing ability in terms of time and accuracy. At the same time, ensure that the system always operates smoothly and stably, ready to meet the transaction needs of customers.

In addition to promoting gift promotions when opening credit cards, Vietcombank needs to pay attention to customer care, ready to help when customers need it. Focus on creating motivation to change customers' habits of using cash, instead using credit cards. Therefore, the content in the promotional programs should emphasize to users clearly the utility of the card, create convenience and peace of mind to use, along with the appropriate cost of using the card.

Tangible means

Tangible means showing the image of NH. This factor plays an important role in the choice of customers with products and services of any bank. Therefore, facilities and equipment need to be embellished and upgraded by Vietcombank, especially the system of ATMs of Vietcombank, POS machines. Each credit class serves different customer segments with a credit card design that needs to be eye-catching, youthful, recognizable and distinctive.

Transaction space should be designed airy, luxurious and modern, ensuring that all transaction offices have the most comfortable customer service space and meet the prescribed standards. At the same time, there must be consistency and consistency from the branch to the transaction offices. At the transaction counters, the space should provide customers with the experience of integrating the modern device ecosystem, while promoting the new service products of Vietcombank. The working style of Vietcombank's staff is professional, reflected in neat manners, knowledge, skills in solving problems effectively, reasonable advice for customers, and friendly communication attitude. , agility will help customers feel comfortable and open to discuss with employees to choose suitable banking products and services.

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References

- ❖ Barbara R. Lewis, and Vincent, W. Mitchell. (1990). Defining and Measuring the Quality of Customer Service, *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 8(6):11-17, DOI:10.1108/EUM000000001086
- ❖ Benjamin Schneider & Susan S. White (2004). *Service Quality: Research Perspectives*, Sage Publications, Inc, USA.
- ❖ Charles Mwatsika (2014), "Customers' satisfaction with ATM banking in Malawi", *African Journal of Business Management*, 8(7), pp. 218-227, 14 April, 2014 DOI: 10.5897/AJBM2014.7412 ISSN 1993-8233.

- ❖ Chew Wen Jing and Leong, Joon Sang and Saw, Melanie Qian Nee and Ng, Pei Qi and Siew, Gao Sheng (2018). Customer satisfaction level towards service quality in credit cards: in the urban area of Malaysia. Final Year Project, UTAR. 16-42.
- ❖ Cronin JJ, Taylor, SA. (1992). "Measuring service quality: a reexamination and extension", *Journal of Marketing*, 56(3), pp.55-68, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1252296>.
- ❖ Fauz Khamis, and Rosemaliza AbRashid (2018). Service quality and customer's satisfaction in Tanzania's Islamic banks: A case study at People's Bank of Zanzibar (PBZ). *Journal of Islamic Marketing* 9(6); 884-900; DOI:10.1108/JIMA-09-2016-0068;
- ❖ Fishbein M, & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research*, Addison-Wesley, Reading, Massachusetts, Buttle F (1996). *Relationship Marketing: Theory and Practice*, Paul Chapman Publishing, London.
- ❖ Gaura Nautiyal (2014). Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in the retail banking sector. *Global Journal of Commerce & Management Perspective*, G.J.C.M.P, 3(3), pp.77-80, ISSN: 2319 – 7285. Corpus ID: 167506021.
- ❖ Grönroos, C. (1984). A Service Quality Model and its Marketing Implications. *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 18 No. 4, pp. 36-44. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM0000000004784>
- ❖ Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2019), "Customer Satisfaction towards ATM Services: A Case of Vietcombank Vinh Long, Vietnam", *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business* 6(1), pp. 141-148, ISSN: 2288-4637 / Online ISSN 2288-4645. DOI: 10.13106/jafeb/2019.vol6.no1.141.
- ❖ Hoang, T., & Chu, N. M. N. (2008). *Analyzing research data with SPSS*, Statistical Publishing House; 14-20.
- ❖ Khan; Fasih (2014), Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: Evidence from banking sector, *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*, 2014, Vol. 8 (2), 331- 354. Corpus ID: 18214969.
- ❖ Le, N. D., Le, D. H., & Vo, T. K. H. (2017). Factors affecting the SHL of science and technology with the quality of domestic debit card services at Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade - Dong Nai Branch, *Scientific Journal and Forestry Technology*, No. 6-2017; 176-186.
- ❖ Le, T. T. H., Nguyen, M. T., Do, H. N., Le, V. T., & Tang, T. N. (2014). Assessment of customer satisfaction with the quality of payment card services of Vietinbank – Can Tho Branch. *Journal of Science Can Tho University, Part D: Political Science, Economics and Law*: 33 (2014): 21-28.
- ❖ Nguyen Viet Hung (2019), Factors affecting customer satisfaction with card services at Agribank Kien Giang, *Financial Review*, [<https://tapchitaichinh.vn/ngan-hang/nhan-to-anh-huong-den-su-hai-long-cua-khach-hang-voi-dich-vu-the-tai-agribank-kien-giang-302725.html>], (Date accessed: 07/06/2021).
- ❖ Nguyen Thanh Vu, Ha Thi Thanh Thuy (2021), Factors affecting customer satisfaction using credit cards at Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Investment and Development of Vietnam - Phu My Hung Branch, *Public Journal love*, [<http://www.tapchicongthuong.vn/bai-viet/cac-yeu-to-anh-huong-den-su-hai-long-cua-khach-hang-su-dung-the-tin-dung-tai-ngan-hang-tmcp-dau-tu-va-phat-trien-viet-nam-chi-nhanh-phu-my-hung-78624.htm>], (Date accessed: 07/06/2021).
- ❖ Nguyen, T. T. (2016). Research on factors affecting customer satisfaction using ATM card services of banks in Hanoi, *Asia - Pacific Economy*, ISSN 0868-3808; 18-25.
- ❖ Oliver, R. L. (1980). A Cognitive Model of the Antecedents and Consequences of Satisfaction Decisions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, (17), pp.460-469. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3150499>
- ❖ Parasuraman A, Zeithaml VA, Berry LL (1988). SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer

perceptions of service quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64, 12-40.

- ❖ Rubogora Felix (2017), “Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction in Selected Banks in Rwanda”, *Journal of Business & Financial Affairs*, DOI: 10.4172/2167-0234.1000246.
- ❖ Sasser, W.E., Olsen, R.P. and Wyckoff, D. D. (1978). *Management of service operations*. Allyn and Bacon, Boston, MA.
- ❖ Tran, T. K. C. (2019). Customer SHL Research on Service Quality at Asia Commercial Bank Dong Nai Branch, *Lac Hong Science Journal* 2019, 01 - 05.
- ❖ Vietcombank (2022). Report on development of international credit cards in the period 2016-2021, Vietcombank annual report, 8-13.
- ❖ Zeithaml, V. A., & Bitner, M. J. (2000). *Services Marketing: Intergrating Customer Focus across the Firm*, New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.